

Recommended citation: Kjelsberg, R., & Kahrs, M. S. (2020). Citizen Engineer - Engineering Students' Motivation Towards an Engineering Career. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1323-1327). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654314.

CITIZEN ENGINEER - ENGINEERING STUDENTS' MOTIVATION TOWARDS AN ENGINEERING CAREER

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Conference Key Areas: *Interdisciplinary Engineering Education, Future Engineering Skills*

Keywords: *Motivation, Bildung*

ABSTRACT

This study asks 427 engineering students about their motivation for becoming engineers. It is centered around the course “Introduction to the engineering profession”, that incorporate some Bildung-related topics. The data suggests that intrinsic motivations connecting to the engineering profession were common, and that many students have the prospect of building, creating or developing as a central motivational factor. The paper suggests using this as a starting point to raise perspectives of engineers as builders also of society and incorporating discussions around the societal role of an engineer. This seems the most fruitful way to dip into the intrinsic motivation of the engineering students when teaching Bildung-oriented topics where they themselves may not immediately see the connection to their role as engineers in the making.

1 INTRODUCTION

Engineers used to be perceived as designers of both actual artefacts and of a prosperous society [1, 2]. Today, the public perception of engineers is perhaps more vague [3]. However, engineers seem to be likened with scientists in the sense that they provide solutions to problems by ‘applying’ a strong sense of rationality and scientific methods [4]. This perception disregards the fact that engineers provide solutions which serve human needs [5]. It also disregards a realisation that has been emerging during the last twenty years – that solutions to problems in the real world requires a holistic approach [6]. These two points imply that engineers would need to understand their roles as engineers in order to cooperate with other professions, and

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also to appreciate the non-technological aspects which often comprise a solution to a problem.

In a broad sense, these topics could be connected to engineering Bildung, understood as a process enabling you to become a *citizen* – an active participant in society, and not simply a vocational practitioner of a craft. This idea is found in both the tradition of classical Bildung and the Anglo-American tradition of liberal education [7-9]. This also explains why some see science and technology as relatively less relevant to Bildung, as many other fields, like the humanities and the social sciences, directly research aspects of society.

All engineering students in Norway take a 10 ECTS-credit course during their first semester – “Introduction to the Engineering Profession”, which contains topics related to engineering Bildung. The first author has been central in developing this course, and has written a textbook in history of science and technology, scientific methods and ethics to cover the course [10].

Earlier experiences with this course have been mixed. The students’ expectations of “usefulness” connected to their professional identity as budding engineers seem to collide with the more Bildung-oriented topics of the course [11]. The aim of this paper is thus to discuss how one could address the students’ initial lack of interest in the non-technical topics within the course in question, by answering the following research questions:

1. What are the motivations of engineering students?
2. How can this knowledge be used to engage students in Bildung-related educational topics?

2 A BRIEF GLANCE AT MOTIVATION

It is common to divide motivation into intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The prior motivation is connected to the joy you get from the task itself; the latter is connected to some form of external reward. A similar affective variable, interest, has been shown to be connected to intrinsic motivation [12].

Several studies over time within different fields have shown that while intrinsic motivation is very positively correlated with better quality work and better performance, a focus on extrinsic rewards may be counterproductive [13-16].

3 METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The university in question is distributed among four campi across Norway, and during the 2019 fall semester the first author was responsible for teaching the introductory part of the course. In total, about 1100 first year engineering students were registered for the course, from all engineering programs and across the four campi.

The students in question all participated in the course “Introduction to the Engineering Profession” during the fall semester of 2019. They were asked to answer in open text “Why do you want to become an engineer?”. In total there were 427 respondents, divided on 4 campi (see table 1).

In analyzing the data, we will use thematic analysis as a method, as discussed by Braun and Clarke [17], searching for recurring themes or patterns within the data, and organizing and interpreting these patterns.

The analysis will be theoretical in the sense that it will make use of the categories of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, but within these categories the search for themes will be inductive.

4 RESULTS

The analysis yields a plurality of motivations that can be divided into intrinsic motivations and extrinsic motivations. The data can however also be divided into personal motivations (what the education can do/does for me) and more societal motivations (environment, contribute to technological development etc.). In Table 1 we extract the societal motivations into a separate theme of motivation named “Altruistic” in addition to the themes intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

Table 1: Responses to "Why do you want to become an engineer?" categorized by type of motivation, by campi and total.

Motivation	Campus 1 (N=176)	Campus 2 (N=101)	Campus 3 (N=46)	Campus 4 (N=104)	Total (N=427)
Intrinsic	116 (66%)	66 (65%)	34 (74%)	70 (67%)	286 (67%)
Extrinsic	58 (33%)	34 (34%)	14 (30%)	34 (33%)	140 (33%)
Altruistic	62 (35%)	20 (20%)	8 (17%)	21 (20%)	107 (25%)

We see that the results, with one exception, are similar across the campi. First of all, many students have answers that fit several categories. They are naturally not exclusive, and many are motivated by e.g. a job that is both interesting and well paid.

Around 2/3 of the students express intrinsic motivations - a personal interest in engineering. We can however see variation within this group. Some students are more interested in the type of work they will be able to do as an engineer after finishing their education. Others express interest in the education in itself. When it comes to exploring this intrinsic motivation further, we see that 1/3 of the students in expressing their intrinsic motivation explicitly mentions building, creating or developing things. The idea of creating seems to be at the core of the motivation of many engineering students. Another subject that appears relatively often in the short open-text answers is the opportunity to combine the theory and praxis in different ways. 1/10th explicitly mentions this as part of their intrinsic motivation for engineering.

Within the category of extrinsic motivations, a good job market, a well-paid job, and a job that brings social status are recurring themes within the 1/3 of students that promote this as a reason for becoming an engineer.

Finally 1/4th of students explicitly expresses a wish to contribute to society as an important motivation for becoming an engineer.

Within a dichotomy of intrinsic/extrinsic motivation the altruistic contribution to society must also be considered an intrinsic motivation, but as a motivation for improving the world rather than a more direct interest in the topics. Adding all

respondents that have registered either intrinsic or altruistic or both as motivations we get that a total of 89% of engineering students according to themselves are driven at least in part by some form of intrinsic motivation. Less than 11% are driven solely of extrinsic motivations.

5 DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

From the results we can identify how 9/10^{ths} of engineering students reports having different forms of intrinsic motivations for studying engineering. As intrinsic motivations have shown to consistently provide better results than extrinsic motivation this should be good news.

However, an intrinsic motivation for becoming an engineer, does not necessarily mean that the students have an intrinsic motivation for this “Introduction to the engineering profession” course. Much of their intrinsic motivation is connected to the job as an engineer - the engineering profession. This is also in line with the referred previous research [11]. It would follow that an important success factor for the Bildung-related topics about different aspects of society is to connect them to the engineering profession.

To further this discussion, we must also look closer into the responses to see where such connections could be made for the overarching subjects of the course, and to promote a Bildung-oriented engineering education. In analyzing the prominent focus on developing, creating etc. in the students’ motivation for becoming an engineer one might ask the question: Could the key to *Bildung* for engineers be in *building*? Their motivation for building and creating could be understood as both building a machine or a structure, and as (contributing to) building a society. As part of the course is about history of technology it thus makes sense to teach this aspect of the history of the engineering profession and promote critical discussions around the contributions to society of different professions historically, and in the present.

There are very few aspects of our society that are untouched by technology, and in extension, by the engineering profession. This should enable teaching Bildung-oriented topics to engineering students on the basis of their professional identity of engineers. Based on the data from this survey, this seems like a promising path towards addressing the perceived lack of “usefulness” some teachers struggle with in this and similar topics.

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